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A study on supply chain management with special reference to Future Group outlet Mangalore.

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Abstract:

Logistics is that part of the supply chain process that plans, implements, and controls the efficient, effective flow of goods, services, and related information from the point-of-origin to the point-of-consumption in order to meet customers' requirements. A good logistics and supply chain team is essential for the success of retail store. The working pattern in logistics department has to be put in place to yield better results and smooth flow of work.

This paper provides general overview of logistics function as well as practices at future group outlets in Mangalore and also tries to identify ideas and a work flow system which might help in improving the efficiency level of the department and there by store performance.

Key words: logistics, supply chain, workflow system, retail outlets

Introduction

Supply chain management (SCM) is the process of planning, implementing and controlling the operations of the supply chain as efficiently as possible. Supply Chain Management spans all the movement and storage of raw materials, work-in-process warehouse, and finished goods from point-of-origin to point-of-consumption. Logistics is that part of the supply chain process. Supply chain management is viewed to lie between fully integrated firms, where the entire material flow is owned by a single firm and those where each channel member operates independently so the coordination between the various players in the chain is key in effective management.

The ultimate success of the store will depend on management's ability to integrate the company's complicated network which has multiple vendors supplying the stocks based on the purchase order generated by the category officer and team as per the stock availability on floor. Distributors have added warehouse to cover unexpected demand coming from retail stores. The more predictable the demand, the easier it is to coordinate activities throughout

the supply chain. The result is better on-time delivery, fewer stock outs, and higher customer satisfaction with less warehouse, reduced administrative work and lower overall costs.

Instead of brand versus brand or store versus store, it is now supply chain versus supply chain. In this emerging highly competitive and dynamic environment. Experience shows that the gains to be made in cost, lead-time and quality through working in partnership with customers and suppliers are significant. One observes that 50%-60% of total costs are supplier related.

Objective of the study

- To study and understand the process followed in receiving and storing the goods in Big Bazaar.
- To study the supply chain structure adopted by Big Bazaar.
- To study the techniques followed in receiving the goods by Big Bazaar.

SUPPLY CHAIN STRUCTURE IN BIG BAZAAR:

The supply chain of the Big Bazaar is quite simple and is designed to minimize the cost of transport and warehouse. The supply chain of Big Bazaar store can be subdivided in the following way:

The above represented structure of the supply chain of Big Bazaar is implemented in store by the Logistics Department and the Category people. Both these departments go hand in hand managing the stock intakes, warehouse management, outgoing stock, and looking for efficient suppliers. The structure followed ensure no problem in making product available for the customers when they walk in to shop the required products

STEPS FOLLOWED IN RECEIVING AND STORING THE GOODS

The department follows a systematic sequence of steps to be followed to avoid human errors and for smooth flow of work which ensures the goods received can be dispatched to floor for sales and also for the inwarding process to update the SAP (system application products) machine on stock available.

Each vendor should enter the department with products as per the purchase order generated by the officer. The vendor has to go through the steps to get the products approved and received. The MRP mentioned and price on the purchase order should be the same. The article number printed on the product should be as per the number printed on product which makes it easy at the billing section to bill the products faster with no stoppage. In case it does not match a barcode is generated by the logistics department and put it on the product for only one and correct barcode to be scan during billing. The quantity ordered and the stock brought has to be counted and should mention the quantity brought to avoid excess cash payment to vendors. The product expiry date is checked to avoid receiving of near expiry products. In some cases its received based on the policy the vendor holds with the stores regarding the near expiry or expired products.

TECHNIQUES FOLLOWED IN RECEIVING THE GOODS

- FIFO – first in and first out method of vendor reporting and getting the goods is followed as per the arrival. The vendors must get products as per purchase order one at a time to avoid confusion regarding the product description and the article number. The department receiving the products is restricted to 9 am to 3 pm after which the executive has to carry out the inwarding of purchase order into the SAP system.
- Logistic Schedule-is prepared by department to each vendor as to when the products have to be brought to the retail store. This has to be coordinated by the category office while generating the purchase order and sending it to vendor accordingly. The vendor getting the products on the wrong day will not be entertained and will be received at the end after all the possible work is done during the time allotted .
- Place for everything and everything in place – the logistics department has specific place for each product to be kept after receiving which indicates the housekeeping team to take the products to floor for display and sale of product. The department also has specific place for products to be kept in case of a MRP mismatch or ANF (Article Not Found) which will be kept separately until the regional head office updates the correct details in the SAP regarding the product.
- Internal weekly audit – with the security department to tally and ensure the errors are identified and rectified by telling the executive the error and the reason for error and how not to repeat the errors. The security also maintains the entries of vendors entering the logistics department records all the moment made while the products are brought and the received by the department. Any rejected products going back with vendor also is recorded which makes it easy to for both the department security and logistics to tally and check if the work is error free. The audit is done by the department manager and the store manager

CONCLUSION

The ultimate success of the store will depend on the efficient work carried out by the logistics and the category officer as a team to ensure the right products are offered with right price with attractive offers. The logistics structure followed by the company helps the company to ensure the products reach the store on time and monitor the activities of logistics department. The department follows the purchase order steps decided earlier. When the goods are received as per the mention or specifications of the stores by matching the MRP and the article number. This reduces the error and the performance can be maintained and improved.

The performance of the department is recorded and reported to the store manager at the time of audit carried out by the company. The score assigned by the auditor is a level of performance as a team put up by the department for that particular period and the aim is to maintain and even better the performance in the audit score. The same supply chain flow for

products to reach the store can be implemented in all the other stores to ensure the overall performance of the store is increased and contributing more towards the profit of the store.

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